

three equal splits at transplanting, active tillering, and panicle initiation.

Crop growth rate was calculated from dry weight recorded at regular intervals. Seedling vigor index was calculated from observations made 1 day before transplanting where

$$\text{Vigor index} = (\text{shoot length} + \text{root length}) \times \text{germination (\%)}$$

Seedlings obtained from nursery beds with a seeding rate of 20 g m⁻² were most vigorous. Their vigor index was 3585 in 1993 and 3269 in 1994, while for seedlings at 40 g m⁻² it was 3129 and 2955 and at 60 g m⁻², 2756 and 2636, respectively.

Grain yield increased significantly as N application rose from 0 to 150 kg ha⁻¹ (see table), although a further increase from 150 to 200 kg N ha⁻¹ did not increase grain yield significantly. Harvest index decreased and spikelet sterility (%) increased progressively with increased N application.

The most vigorous seedlings (from 20 g m⁻² seeding rate) produced significantly higher grain yield (6.8 t ha⁻¹) than did those from the higher seeding rates. The weakest seedlings produced the lowest yield (6.1 t ha⁻¹). The harvest index was highest and sterility lowest in the most vigorous seedlings.

The crop growth rate increased as the N rate was increased from 0 to 200 kg ha⁻¹ (see figure). The highest rate was recorded with 200 kg N⁻¹ ha between 61 and 80 d in 1993 and 41 and 60 d in 1994. After attaining maximum values, the crop growth rate decreased drastically during the final time interval during both years. Seedlings from the 20 g m⁻² seeding rate generally had a higher crop growth rate during the times of maximum growth. ■

Effects of N levels and nursery seeding rate on grain yield and harvest index of hybrid rice.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Harvest index		Sterility (%)	
	1993	1994	Mean	1993	1994	1993	1994
<i>N level (kg ha⁻¹)</i>							
0	4.0	3.4	3.7	0.61	0.59	21.6	27.0
50	5.7	5.4	5.6	0.60	0.58	24.5	29.7
100	7.2	6.8	7.0	0.59	0.57	26.3	31.0
150	8.0	7.5	7.8	0.55	0.54	27.3	33.6
200	8.3	7.7	8.0	0.54	0.52	27.9	33.6
LSD (0.05)	0.4	0.3		0.01	0.01	2.5	2.7
<i>Nursery seeding rate (g m⁻²)</i>							
20	7.1	6.5	6.8	0.59	0.57	21.6	30.0
40	6.5	6.2	6.4	0.58	0.56	25.6	31.1
60	6.3	5.9	6.1	0.57	0.56	26.6	31.6
LSD (0.05)	0.4	0.2	-	0.01	0.01	2.3	2.6

Effects of N levels and nursery seeding rate on crop growth rate (g m⁻² d⁻¹).

Integrated pest management—diseases

Fine and physical mapping toward the positional cloning of an indica-derived blast resistance gene *Pi-b*

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Rice blast is one of the most devastating diseases of rice, especially in temperate areas. Therefore, abundant genetic data on rice blast resistance genes have been

accumulated in Japan. The indica-derived resistance genes introgressed into japonica backgrounds showed a wide spectrum of resistance and provided excellent materials for mapping the introgressed genes.

We took *Pi-b* as a target for mapping and obtained two cosegregating markers and very close flanking markers on both sides. By using them, a contig of cosmid library clones was constructed around the gene.

Restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) and random amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) analysis of near-isogenic lines (NILs) with *Pi-b*. The blast resistance gene *Pi-b* was introgressed from two Malaysian and two Indonesian cultivars into a japonica background by repeated backcrosses; several NILs were developed. It was suggested that the gene was on the end of chromosome 2 (Shinoda et al 1971).

We studied patterns of RFLP markers around the region and summarized their results as a graphical genotype map (Fig. 1). To obtain markers closer to *Pi-b*, RAPD markers were sought using 800 polymerase chain reaction primers, and a marker cosegregating with *Pi-b* in all the NILs was found and named b-1 (Fig. 1). Although *Pi-b* was introgressed from four cultivars in Malaysia and Indonesia, the nonjaponica type RFLP patterns were identical among the four lines, suggesting a single origin of the gene in all of the cultivars.

Fine mapping of *Pi-b* by F_2 analysis. Through F_2 analysis of 122 susceptible individuals (recessive homozygous) from the crosses of BL1/Nourin 22 and Aichi Asahi/BL1, the map distances between the *Pi-b* and nearby RFLP/RAPD markers were determined with an accuracy of 0.4 cM (Fig. 2a). RZ123 and b-1 cosegregated with *Pi-b*. The centromeric and telomeric flanking markers G1234 and RZ213 were 0.4 cM and 1.9 cM from the gene, respec-

1. Graphical genotype of the indica region introgressed into NILs with *Pi-b*. b1; RAPD marker, RZ, RG; Cornell University markers. G, cDK; RGP markers.

2. Fine mapping of *Pi-b* with F_2 analyses with 170 susceptible individuals (a), and a contig constructed from the cosmid library (b).

tively. Large-fragment Southern blotting indicated RZ123 and b-1 are on the same fragment of 85 kb.

Cosmid library of rice genome. A genomic cosmid library was constructed with an average insert size of 38 kb, with 5 genome equivalents using pWE 15 as a vector. RZ123 and b-1 were shown to be on the same clone. Four steps of walking were

done by the TAIL method (Liu et al 1994) to amplify the end portions of the inserts, and 100 kb was covered (Fig. 2b).

Cited references

- Liu, Y-G and R Wittier. 1995. Genomics. 25:674-681.
 Shinoda H et al. 1971. Bull. Chugoku Agric. Exp. Stn. Ser. A20: 1-25 [Jpn/Eng]. ■

Effect of botanicals on managing sheath rot of rice

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We evaluated the efficacy of neem derivatives, such as neem oil (3%) and neem seed kernel extract (5%); leaf extracts (10%) from Nochi (*Vitex negundo*), white babul (*Acacia leucocephala*) and polyalthia (*Polyalthia longifolia*); standard fungicide carbendazim (500 g ha⁻¹); and insecticide monocrotopos (500 ml ha⁻¹) to control sheath rot caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) W. Gams and D. Hawksw.

Susceptible cultivar ADT36 was planted in the field during 1994-95. Leaf extracts, carbendazim, and monocrotopos were applied as foliar sprays at booting and 2 wk later. Each treatment was replicated three times.

Sheath rot incidence was measured as the percentage of tillers affected in 25 randomly selected hills plot⁻¹ at 20 d after the last spray.

All treatments significantly reduced sheath rot compared with the control (see

Effect of botanicals on sheath rot incidence.

Treatment	Dose (%)	Mean sheath rot incidence (%)	Mean grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Neem oil	3	8.18	5.1
Neem seed kernel extract	5	7.79	5.7
Nochi	10	11.25	6.3
White babul	10	8.14	6.1
<i>Polyalthia</i>	10	10.83	6.1
Carbendazim	500 g ha ⁻¹	4.71	6.6
Monocrotopos	500 ml ha ⁻¹	14.54	5.7
Untreated control	-	18.58	5.1
CD (P = 0.05)		2.88	0.9